

Fourier transform-infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy : A superior analytical technique for quantitative estimation of cefditoren pivoxil and its pharmaceutical formulations

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Abstract : A Transmission Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrometric method was developed for the rapid and direct measurement of cefditoren pivoxil in pharmaceutical formulation. Sample preparation for FTIR measurements is simple and use of toxic solvents is avoided. Beer's law was applied in the FTIR region from 1810 to 1760 cm^{-1} for calibration development. A good calibration curve with linear regression of 0.996 was obtained for the standards in the range of 0.005–1.0 mg. The results of the study clearly reveal the capability of Transmission FTIR spectroscopy in direct determination of cefditoren pivoxil in pharmaceutical formulation and finished products.

Keywords : FTIR, cefditoren pivoxil, formulations, estimation, TQ analyst.

Introduction

Cefditoren pivoxil ($\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_6\text{O}_7\text{S}_3$) is a third generation semi-synthetic cephalosporin antibiotic to treat uncomplicated skin and skin structure diseases, pharyngitis, tonsillitis, community-acquired pneumonia and acute bacterial exacerbation of chronic bronchitis¹. The molecular weight of cefditoren pivoxil is 620.73 and chemical structure is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of cefditoren pivoxil.

Literature survey reveals that various analytical methods are developed for determination of cefditoren pivoxil from pharmaceutical formulations such as RP-HPLC²⁻⁶,

UPLC⁷, HPTLC^{8,9}, XRD¹⁰ and visible spectroscopy¹¹. Although HPLC was found to be precious tool for determination of drugs from pharmaceutical formulations, the time consumption, sample preparation and use of toxic solvents are the drawbacks of the technique. Use of spectrometric methods can be rapid and cost effective for analysis of finished pharmaceutical products. In last few years, FTIR spectroscopy has achieved much recognition as rapid analytical technique in the laboratories of pharmaceutical industries for qualitative analysis of raw and finished products¹². Recent development of sophisticated software has constructed FTIR spectroscopy as a rapid and straightforward technique for quantitative determination of drugs from its pharmaceutical formulations. Therefore the present study was undertaken to develop a rapid, cheap, accurate and eco-friendly analytical technique for routine determination of cefditoren pivoxil from tablet formulations without use of any toxic solvents.

Materials and methods :

Reagents and samples :

Analytical grade Cefditoren pivoxil standard used for calibration in the present study was obtained from Hetero Drugs Pvt. Ltd., Hyderabad. Commercially available tab-

lets containing Cefditoren pivoxil as an active ingredient were purchased from local medical stores. Sample pellets for FTIR analysis was prepared using IR spectroscopic grade KBr purchased from Merck Ltd.

FT-IR spectral measurements :

Thermo Nicolet Avatar 330 FTIR spectrometer equipped with KBr optics and deuterated triglycine sulfate (DTGS) detector was used for acquisition of infrared spectra of standards as well as samples in the tablet form. The instrument was controlled by commercially available IR spectra analysis software package EZ-OMNIC (Thermo Nicolet Analytical Instruments, Madison, USA). Atmospheric suppression for FTIR spectrum of each standard and sample was done by fresh background spectrum recorded from KBr pellet. All spectra were recorded in the Mid IR region from 4000–400 cm^{-1} averaging 32 scans at a spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} at 25 °C \pm 2 temperature.

FT-IR calibrations :

FTIR calibrations are performed as per the method proposed by Sherazi *et al.*¹³. A set of 14 standards of cefditoren pivoxil containing the range between 0.005 and 1.0 mg in KBr was prepared to formulate the 100 mg pellets of total weight. Simple Beer's law was employed for the quantitative determination of cefditoren pivoxil in tablet formulation by EZ-OMNIC and TQ Analyst program (Thermo Electron Corporation, USA). In the TQ Analyst program cefditoren pivoxil standards ranging from 0.005 to 1.0 mg were selected, that were already recorded. For best quantitative determination, specific carbonyl band i.e. 1810–1760 cm^{-1} was specified in the TQ Analyst program which is a better option to save the time and labor to measure peak height, peak width and peak area as compare to manual calculations. Area under the band for all cefditoren pivoxil standards were calculated by the TQ Analyst software itself. Through cross validation, an excellent calibration curve was obtained between actual and predicted values of cefditoren pivoxil standards.

Sample preparation :

The major advantage of FTIR technique is mere sample preparation procedure. The weighed tablet samples were fine powdered using a mortar and accurately weighed 1 mg tablet samples was mixed with 99 mg of oven dried KBr. A homogenous mixture of sample and KBr was

obtained by grinding in mortar. Later the mixture was prepared into translucent 13 mm disc by applying 6 tons of pressure for 5 min using KBr press provided with the FTIR spectrometer. The prepared translucent discs were recorded in the Mid IR range from 4000–400 cm^{-1} on Thermo Nicolet Avatar 330 FTIR spectrometer.

Limit of detection and quantification :

The limit of detection (LOD), described as the minimum concentration from which it is possible to deduce the presence of the analyte with reasonable statistical certainty. To determine the limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) for the proposed method, the selected band area was measured at low concentration of standards, until the cefditoren pivoxil related signal disappeared. The analysis at the lowest amount which produced substantial peak was repeated for eleven times and LOD was calculated by the following formula¹⁴ :

$$\text{LOD} = 3 \times \text{SD} \times (\text{C/M})$$

where SD is the standard deviation, C is the concentration of analyte and M is the mean band area.

Similarly, LOQ was determined by the following equation :

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \text{SD} \times (\text{C} \times \text{M})$$

Recovery efficiency :

The recovery efficiency was determined by the ratio of cefditoren pivoxil recovered (%) to the cefditoren pivoxil content (mg) added. The calculation was carried out by the following equation :

$$\text{R\%} = \left(\frac{\text{C} - \text{B}}{\text{A}} \right) \times 100$$

where R is the cefditoren pivoxil recovered (%), A is added level of cefditoren pivoxil, B is the actual concentration of cefditoren pivoxil present in the sample and C is the concentration of cefditoren pivoxil after addition.

Results and discussion

Determination of the major component in drugs with FTIR spectrometry provides an enormous amount of spectroscopic information about the sample. FTIR now recognized as rapid analytical technique for both qualitative and quantitative analysis due to outstanding performances of recently developed software. The results of the present study accomplish the use of FTIR spectroscopy in rapid

and simple measurements of quantity of desired active ingredient while performing quality control of pharmaceuticals.

The FTIR spectrum of cefditoren pivoxil standards recorded in the mid IR region is shown in Fig. 2. The FTIR spectrum shows number of peaks at different wave numbers which corresponds to different functional groups present in cefditoren pivoxil. Similarly, FTIR spectrum of tablets containing cefditoren pivoxil as active ingredient was also recorded (Fig. 3b). The excipients commonly used for the solid commercial formulation are sodium caseinate, starch, magnesium stearate, mannitol, sodium tripoly phosphate, avecil and talcum powder. The FTIR spectrum of mixed excipients is shown in Fig. 3a. It is observed that the carbonyl band at $1810\text{--}1760\text{ cm}^{-1}$ present in commercial tablet and cefditoren pivoxil standard is not observed in the FTIR spectrum of mixed excipients without cefditoren pivoxil. The absence of significant interference band in mixed excipients has proven the method to be practical, rapid, direct and green.

The carbonyl band selected in FTIR region from $1810\text{--}1760\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for quantification of cefditoren pivoxil standards (0.005 to 1.0 mg) is shown in Fig. 4.

The availability of sophisticated software techniques has made the present work more rapid and simple. The FTIR spectrums recorded for standards were opened in TQ Analyst as it is able to generate the calibration in an easy and efficient way. For quantitative determination of cefditoren pivoxil in the pharmaceutical formulation a simple Beer's law was employed based on the measurement of carbonyl band area. A good calibration curve with excellent linear regression was obtained. The calibration curve with percentage difference plot between the actual and calculated values for the range of 0.005–1.0 mg calibration standards obtained through TQ Analyst is presented in Fig. 5. A good calibration curve with linear regression of 0.996 shows the tremendous sensitivity of FTIR spectroscopy for the determination of cefditoren pivoxil in pharmaceutical formulations.

From calibration, the assessment of the errors was carried out by calculating the residual mean standard er-

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of cefditoren pivoxil standards in mid IR region.

Fig. 3. FTIR spectra of (a) mixture of excipients (i.e. sodium caseinate, magnesium stearate, avicel, talcum powder and starch etc.), (b) cefditoren pivoxil in tablet formulations, (c) cefditoren pivoxil standard.

Fig. 4. Response of the carbonyl band area to various concentrations of the cefditoren pivoxil standards by FTIR spectroscopy.

Fig. 5. TQ Analyst calibration graph of cefditoren pivoxil standards.

ror of calibration (RMSEC) after comparing the actual concentration with the computed one for each component with the standard deviation of 0.029. The root mean square error of prediction (RMSEP) was $0.58e^{-3}$ and the quantitative model also verified through root mean square error of cross validation (RMSECV) which was found to be 0.036. The low error values obtained from the calibration shows the appropriateness to the present method for quantitative determination of cefditoren pivoxil by FTIR spectroscopy.

The quantification of cefditoren pivoxil from tablets was carried using the regression equation obtained from the calibration of standards. The summary of the results obtained by the present method for cefditoren pivoxil is presented in Table 1. The concentration of cefditoren pivoxil determined was found to be in the range of 97.35–99.55% for labeled commercial tablets.

The LOD and LOQ were calculated from this method was found to be 0.007 mg g^{-1} and 0.021 mg g^{-1} respectively for cefditoren pivoxil. Recovery test was used further for evaluation of the accuracy of the method. The comparison of recovery of cefditoren pivoxil from tablet samples with the analytical techniques is presented in Table 2. The high percentage recovery revealed that there is no significant interference band from any other excipients present in the formulation hence evidence that this method is feasible for direct and rapid determination.

Table 1. Analysis of cefditoren pivoxil commercial formulation (Tablets)

Sample	Labeled claim (mg)	Amount recovered	Recovery (%)
Zostum-O	200	194.7	97.35
Cefditran	200	199.1	99.55
Ceftorin	200	197.5	98.75

Table 2. Comparison of recovery of cefditoren pivoxil from tablet samples with other analytical techniques

Analytical technique	Recovery (%)	Ref.
RP-HPLC	99.20	3
RP-HPLC	99.62	4
HPTLC	98.24	8
Visible spectrophotometer	99.25	16
FTIR	98.75	This study

Conclusion

The present method for determination of cefditoren pivoxil in tablets using FTIR spectroscopy was found to be simple, rapid and eco-friendly technique. The high percentage recoveries of cefditoren pivoxil from pharmaceutical formulations reveal the feasibility of the present model. This results show that FTIR spectroscopy can be a potential analytical technique for qualitative and quantitative analysis of cefditoren pivoxil in pharmaceutical formulations.

References

1. E. A. Balbisi, *Pharmacotherapy*, 2002, **22**, 1278.
2. N. Srinivasa Rao and K. Saraswathi, *J. Pharm. Sci. Res.*, 2011, **3**, 1002.
3. P. Dewani, N. I. Kochar, H. C. Abooj, R. L. Bakal, A. V. Chandewar and B. B. Barik, *J. Pharm. Res.*, 2010, **3**, 2588.
4. M. M. Annapurna, S. V. S. Goutam, S. Anusha and L. Srinivas, *J. Pharm. Anal.*, 2012, **2**, 466.
5. W. Rieck and D. Platt, *Clin Lab.*, 2000, **46**, 477.
6. S. Vidhya, B. L. Narayanan, P. Malairajan, R. J. Sahayaraja, E. P. Kumar, S. Mahibalan, M. Karpakavalli and C. Balakumar, *Int. J. Drug Dev. Res.*, 2012, **4**, 186.
7. R. Garg, N. Singh, K. S. Srinivas, B. Deb and A. Ahmed, *J. Appl. Pharm. Sci.*, 2011, **1**, 149.
8. P. S. Narayana, A. S. Reddy and R. Sekar, *J. Pharm. Res.*, 2012, **5**, 1628.
9. S. Kitahar, T. Ishizukaa, T. Kikkojia, R. Matsudab and Y. Hayashi, *Int. J. Pharmaceu.*, 2004, **283**, 63.
10. D. Madhra Vishal, S. P. Anurath and M. Ashwini, *Int. J. Res. Ayur. Pharm.*, 2011, **2**, 1582.
11. S. A. Raju, A. B. Karadi and S. Manjunath, *J. Indian Council Chem.*, 2009, **26**, 54.
12. O. Y. Rodionova, L. P. Houmøller, A. L. Pomerantsev, P. Geladi, J. Burger, V. L. Dorofeyev and A. P. Arzamastsev, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2005, **549**, 151.
13. S. T. H. Sherazi, M. Ali and S. A. Mahesar, *Vibrational Spectroscopy*, 2011, **55**, 115.
14. N. N. Memon, S. T. H. Sherazi, F. N. Talpur and M. I. Bhangar, *J. Assoc. Offic. Anal. Chem.*, 2010, **258**, 1249.
15. AOAC International, Association of Official Analytical Chemists, Arlington, VA, 2002.
16. V. Niraimathi, A. Aruna, A. J. Suresh and V. Prema, *Int. J. Chem. Sci.*, 2010, **8**, 724.